

Uzbek National Wrestling is Facing the World

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Abstract: This article is about Uzbek national wrestling. The legends of the origin and history of the sport and its development over the centuries, the essence of the meaning, as well as the importance of this sport today, the attention paid to it, its impact on the consciousness and spirituality of young people, and the development of this sport. and the technique of national wrestling.

Key points: Defeat, trickery, defense, counter-attack, “Compulsory training in martial arts” decision, “Bukhara” method, “Fergana” method, Surkhan method.

There are many national sports in the world. But it took several decades for them to become popular. Thanks to independence, the noble goal of restoring our ancient values in our country and spreading them widely is also bearing great fruit today. In particular, in order to widely popularize the national sport - wrestling, international tournaments were organized in Shahrisabz for the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Prize in memory of Amir Temur and in Termez in memory of Al-Hakim At-Termizi. After that, Uzbek wrestling was widely demonstrated at major sports conferences in countries such as South Korea, Canada, Japan, India, the USA, and Russia. As a result, on September 6, 1998, the world community officially recognized Uzbek wrestling as an international sport. At the founding congress, which was held with the participation of representatives of 28 countries from Asia, Europe, and the Americas, the International Wrestling Association (IWA) was founded.

In 1999, the International Wrestling Association had more than 100 member states, more than 120 countries recognized the IWA and are working together. The Dutchman Frans Hugendeuk wrote in his letter: “Personally, I can confidently call wrestling a sport of the 21st century.”

The Decree of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov on supporting the International Wrestling Association “Kurash” in 1999 serves as an important program for the further development of national wrestling. That year, the 1st World Wrestling Championship was held in our capital. Wrestlers from about fifty countries of the planet competed for the victory. In the competitions held in three weight categories, our compatriots Akobir Kurbanov, Kamol Murodov and Toshtemir Muhammadiyev received the high honor of world champion. After that, the world championships in Uzbek national wrestling were hosted by the cities of Antalya, Budapest, Yerevan, Ulan Bator and Alushta. Also, international tournaments for the Islam Karimov Prize in wrestling are being held in Great Britain and Greece.

This is evidence of the rapid popularity of Uzbek wrestling on a global scale. At the same time, the International Association of “Kurash” attached special importance to the widespread popularization of this sport on five continents of the world, thereby promoting our national values and traditions.

Today, wrestling confederations operate on five continents of our planet, and wrestling federations operate in more than 130 countries. If you go to any country in the world now, you will witness wrestlers wearing Uzbek national wrestling uniforms in gyms, bowing to the mat with their hands on their chests, or you will witness the resounding of pure Uzbek words such as “halol”, “chala”, “yonbosh”, “girrom”, “dakki” in world arenas. In particular, the statement by the President of the International Olympic Committee, Jacques Rogge, that “the doors of the International Olympic

Committee are always open for such a wonderful sport as wrestling" is the most worthy assessment given to this national sport. Undoubtedly, this is also a historical achievement of our Independent Uzbekistan.

The fact that wrestling, which has become a world sport in the name of our nation, is rapidly developing in more than 100 countries of the world today makes those who claim to be involved in the glory of our Motherland proud. Well, what is the secret - the art of Uzbek sport wrestling, which today has become an equal member of the world sports family. Of course, the main factor in the work done to gain prestige and respect for our ancient value, wrestling, in the international arena, its inclusion in the Asian, African, Pan-American sports games, and its inclusion in the Olympic sports family, and the results achieved is the independence of our homeland. Looking at the work being done to develop a particular sport in the international arena, to take its place in the Asian and Olympic Games, one feels proud. On November 5, 2020, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop the national sport of wrestling and further increase its international prestige" was adopted. In order to pass on to future generations the rich traditions and values of wrestling inherited from our great ancestors, to increase the role of wrestling in the world arena under the name of the Uzbek sports brand, and to support and encourage young people's interest in national sports, in accordance with the Presidential Resolution, it was determined that an international competition among students of higher educational institutions in wrestling will be held every two years from 2021. International tournaments for the Prize of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan are being held in foreign countries, and since 2020, the "Uzbek Polvoni" republican competition among employees of state bodies, institutions and organizations is being held once a year. Starting from 2021, kurash mastery schools are being gradually established in localities. In order to train qualified coaches and Olympic reserves, the International Wrestling Institute was established under the auspices of the International Wrestling Association and the Uzbekistan Wrestling Federation.

The parameters of the current state order for admission to training in wrestling at the Uzbek State University of Physical Education and Sports, specialized boarding schools of the Olympic reserve, and specialized children's and youth sports schools have been doubled. A wrestling specialty has been opened at the Uzbek State University of Physical Education and Sports and other higher educational institutions with existing physical culture areas. From the 2021/2022 academic year, the parameters of the state order for admission to training in wrestling at the Uzbek State University of Physical Education and Sports, boarding schools, and sports schools have been doubled.

With the participation of law enforcement officers involved in wrestling, free wrestling groups were organized in secondary educational institutions under the slogan "Many countries will be powerful with their wrestlers." In order to popularize the wrestling inherited from our ancestors on the international stage and further increase its prestige, systematic work has been carried out over the past years within the framework of the Presidential Decree "On measures to develop the national sport of wrestling and further increase its international prestige". The inclusion of wrestling in the program of these games, which has the status of a "mini-Olympics", is also an important step towards the widespread popularization of our national sport on the international stage. In 2020, the concept of bringing the national sport of wrestling to a new level by 2025 was approved. The concept includes tasks to achieve one of the eternal dreams of the Uzbek people - the inclusion of the national sport of wrestling in the program of the International Olympic Games. The concept envisages the inclusion of kurash in the International Olympic Games program in 2028. The International Association of National Wrestling, which was established due to independence, has radically changed the spiritual outlook of our people, created confidence in the development of brave, iron-minded, physically strong, and honorable wrestlers of our people in the new national wrestling, and in the realization of the dreams and hopes of a young, harmonious generation embodying national values.

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